

EXERCISE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN COLLEGE STUDENTS

by

Angela Foanene

ORCID ID: 0009-0001-9475-7279

DOI: 10.5381/zenodo.6543726

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2024

Approved by:

Dr. Valerie Poynor, Department of Mathematics

Dr. Stacy Mallicoat, Director University Honors Program

Date:

05/17/24

5/24/2024

Exercise and Academic Performance in College Students

Angela Foanene

Advisor: Valerie Poynor

Abstract

Academic performance in college students is a fundamental goal in universities striving to prepare young members of society for entering the workforce. Many factors influence student academic performance such as study habits, financial responsibilities, and lifestyle. In our research, we examine the relationship between exercise and academic performance in CSUF students. The relationship between exercise and academic performance has been well-studied in adolescents; however, limited literature exists for college students. This study aims to observe the potential correlation between weekly exercise duration and academic performance (via GPA) in undergraduate students. Data were collected through an online volunteer survey in which students answered questions regarding their amount of weekly exercise and their current GPA along with a number of control variable questions. We compare population means via a t-test and assess factor effects via regression analysis. Our finding suggests that both type of exercise and duration may play a role in GPA. In particular, students who engage in both aerobic and strength training for a moderate duration (240-480 min/week) have a 10.4% higher GPA compared to those who do not exercise at all ($p=0.01$). When other survey variables are controlled for, results show similar evidence, but are not significant ($p=0.15$). Given the evidence shown in our analysis, we advocate that further analysis with more data be conducted.

1 Introduction

Student success is an essential aspect of higher education, with academic performance, specifically, GPA, serving a fundamental indicator of achievement and progress. Understanding the factors that influence academic success is crucial for educators in order to uphold the university goal of preparing individuals for the workforce. The brain's remarkable capacity for adaptation, known as neuroplasticity, has been extensively studied in relation to physical activity. Research suggests that consistent moderate exercise can enhance neuroplasticity, potentially leading to improvements in cognitive function and academic outcomes [4, 8].

The enhancement of the brain and cognitive functions has been a topic of interest for many researchers in education and public health. Exercise and physical activity have been noted as a process that has positive effects on cognitive function and the prevention of cognitive decline [3]. Previously conducted animal studies have indicated that the neurobiology, learning ability, and memory of rodents were affected by their environment, especially the presence of a running wheel. These studies have led to the hypothesis that the brain and overall cognitive function of humans can also be influenced by environmental enrichment [3]. Moderate evidence from previously conducted research studies indicates there is a consistent association between amount of physical activity and improved brain function through the use of achievement and neuropsychological tests [7].

Additionally, studies focusing on adolescents have shown that even short periods of moderate to vigorous physical activity during school hours can positively impact academic performance, highlighting the tie between physical activity and educational outcomes [9]. Moreover, recent findings demonstrated the beneficial effects of high-intensity physical activities on mental health, including reductions in anxiety and depression among college students. Exercise is a broad concept, and its correlation to cognitive performance should not be limited to the age group consisting of adolescent children [6, 1]. There does not seem to be many studies that emphasize the correlation between exercise and academic success in young adults or college students. Therefore, this research aims to fill this gap by investigating the

relationship between exercise and academic performance in college students, addressing the need for more studies in this age group.

In summary, this paper aims to investigate the relationship between exercise and GPA among college students. In Section 2, we describe methods used in this research, including our data collection procedures, data visualization and summary statistics, and formal statistical analyses. In Section 3, we present the results of our statistical findings, assess our model assumptions, and provide conclusions of our findings. In Section 4, we provide a discussion on the limitations of our data and future work. This research seeks to provide valuable insights into the potential impact of exercise on academic performance in college students.

2 Methods

2.1 Data Collection

Our data were collected on CSUF undergraduate students through an online voluntary response survey. Before initiating the data collection process, we obtained approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) under #HSR-22-23-403 to ensure compliance with ethical standards for the university. Once IRB approval was obtained, we were able to conduct our online student survey from an anonymous online survey called Qualtrics. Again, the survey was a voluntary response survey available online to students, and responses were collected anonymously. To promote broad participation, emails were sent to a subset of professors from different colleges, during early September 2023, requesting instructors to encourage their students to participate in the survey. Included in the email to professors was a link to the survey link and pre-written email to students. Additionally, paper handouts with a QR code linking to the survey were provided to students in classrooms that we visited upon request of the professors. The survey was accessible through smart phones or computers. Paper handouts were also placed at the U-RISE office in the McCarthy Building and passed out in various classrooms. The survey was available for respondents from September 2023

through October 2023.

Participation in the survey was entirely voluntary and anonymous. The survey encompassed demographics, lifestyle factors, and self-assessed stress level variables, as well as questions regarding exercise habits and GPA. To control for potential confounding variables, such as age, study hours, and stress level, these variables were included in our statistical model. The pre-written student email/announcement outlined the purpose and aim of the research study and any potential risks involved should students choose to participate in the study. Consent was obtained through a preliminary question within the online survey, ensuring that only consenting students proceeded to answer the survey questions. We obtained a total of 200 responses; 112 of those were complete cases and utilized in our analysis. Effort was made to obtain a representative sample of the student population; however, the nature of a voluntary response survey will inevitably come with some level of bias and confounding/lurking variables, which we discuss in Section 5.

2.2 Data Visualization and Summaries

In this section we provide graphical and statistical summaries of the variables in our survey data. Figure 1 displays correlations amongst GPA and explanatory factor variables. The variables that have notable correlations with the response variable, GPA, are age and class standing. There are no other notably moderate to strong correlations between GPA and the other explanatory variables. Furthermore, there appears to be no correlation between our variables of interest, which are exercise type and exercise duration, in regard to the response variable GPA. This led us to look at these two variables more jointly rather than separately in our statistical model detailed in Section 2.3. It is important to point out that, correlation is a measure of a linear association [2]; therefore, any non-linear association cannot be determined by Figure 1.

Figure 1: Correlations amongst GPA and explanatory factor variables.

To assess potential non-linear associations and to further explore the the distribution of GPA across the explanatory factor variables, we provide side-by-side boxplots in Figure 2 and Figure 3. In Figure 2, the x-axis depicts the explanatory factor variables: age (top right), gender (top middle), dependants (top right), class standing (middle left), hours spent studying (middle right), stress level (bottom left), and major college (bottom right). The y- axis for each plot represents GPA. We can see that as age increases, GPA tends to decrease. Similarly, this is seen in class standing and GPA: freshmen tend to have higher GPAs, followed by sophomores then junior, and seniors tend to have the lowest GPA. Looking at the plot for GPA and financial dependents, we can see that students with financial dependent(s) have a notably lower GPA compared to those who do not. Gender and hours spent studying do not appear to be associated with GPA. When we look at stress level, we can see that a group of respondents reported a stress level higher than the range provided, and this group

also shows a slightly lower GPA. Students in the college of Arts appear to have concentrated higher GPA compared to other colleges, while NSM and Engineering/Computer Science students have a relatively lower median GPA with wider spread, and a few lower outliers.

Figure 2: Boxplots of GPA by age (top left), gender (top middle), dependents (top right), class standing (middle left), hours spent studying (middle right), stress level (bottom left), and major college (bottom right).

The plots in Figure 3 show exercise duration (x-axis) and exercise duration (color coded) by GPA on the y-axis. The left figure displays time as a continuous variable with smoothed splines for each exercise type overlaid and dotted vertical lines representing the discretized times bins. The red represents the baseline group of no exercise, green represents both aerobic and strength training, blue represents one of aerobic or strength training, and purple represents another form of exercise. Students who do not exercise, have a GPA ranging from about 2.8 to 4.0 with median around 3.7. The smoothed splines show that, for students who exercise, GPA starts off around the same or higher GPA as those who don't exercise, but as duration increases GPA trends down until about 240min/wk. For students who engage in

both aerobic and strength training, exhibit an increase in GPA after 240 min/wk and hit the highest peak in GPA around 360 min/wk, just slightly above the other form of exercise group. The other exercise type students tend to plateau in GPA after 240min/wk. The right plot in Figure 3 is similar to the left, but displays the time as discrete: none (0 min/wk), minimal (>0-120 min/wk), low (>120-240 min/wk), moderate (>240-360 min/wk), and high (>360 min/wk). Here, we note that students who workout for a moderate duration performing both aerobic and strength training have a consistently higher GPA compared to those who do not work out at all.

Figure 3: GPA by exercise duration and color coded by exercise type. The left figure displays time as a continuous variable with smoothed splines for each exercise type overlaid, and dotted vertical lines representing the discretized times bins. The right figure displays the time as discrete: None (0 min/wk), Minimal (> 0-120 min/wk), Low (> 120-240 min/wk), Moderate (> 240 -360 min/wk), and High (> 360 min/wk).

Table 1 displays summary statistics for each explanatory factor variable: sample size from each population with percentage of total sample size in given in column 2 and mean GPA with standard error is given in column 3. Consistent with Figure 2, we see a decrease in GPA as age increases across groups 18-20 years old (mean = 3.7), 21-25 years old (mean = 3.4), to 26-25 years old (mean = 2.6). We have a small sample size for students having other gender, having dependent(s), and in the college of education. Looking at the stress variable, we note that nearly 85% of student respondents reported a stress level of 4 or higher on a 0 to 5 scale. Students who workout for a minimal weekly duration have the highest GPA (3.7) compared to the other duration groups, and students who engage in both aerobic and

strength training have the highest GPA (3.7) compared to the other exercise types.

Variable	N (%)	Mean GPA (SE)
Age (years)		
18 -20	80(72.1)	3.7(0.04)
21 -25	27(24.3)	3.4(0.07)
26 -35	4(3.6)	2.6(0.20)
Gender		
Male	44(39.6)	3.5(0.08)
Female	65(58.6)	3.6(0.04)
Other	2(1.8)	4.0(0.00)
Class Standing		
Freshman	50(45.1)	3.8(0.05)
Sophomore	12(10.8)	3.6(0.08)
Junior	10(9.0)	3.6(0.10)
Senior	39(35.1)	3.3(0.08)
Exercise Duration		
None	17(15.3)	3.5(0.10)
Minimal	18(16.22)	3.7(0.07)
Low	30(27.0)	3.4(0.10)
Moderate	22(19.8)	3.4(0.08)
High	24(21.6)	3.6(0.09)
Stress Level (0 -5)		
2	7(6.3)	3.7(0.16)
3	9(8.1)	3.7(0.15)
4	42(37.8)	3.6(0.06)
5	39(35.1)	3.6(0.06)
6	14(12.6)	3.3(0.16)
Dependent(s)		
Yes	3(2.7)	2.9(0.44)
No	108(97.3)	3.6(0.04)
Studying (hrs/wk)		
0 -5	20(18.0)	3.6(0.09)
5 -10	41(37.0)	3.4(0.09)
10 -15	29(26.1)	3.6(0.06)
15 -20	14(12.6)	3.6(0.09)
> 20	7(6.3)	3.9(0.07)
Major College		
ART	3(2.7)	3.9(0.06)
BUS/ECON	13(11.7)	3.8(0.09)
COMM	4(3.6)	3.5(0.13)
EDU	1(0.9)	3.9(<i>NA</i>)
ENG/CPSC	20(18.0)	3.6(0.11)
HE/HUDV	10(9.0)	3.7(0.13)
HUM/SOSC	22(19.8)	3.5(0.09)
NSM	38(34.2)	3.5(0.08)
Exercise Type		
None	17(15.3)	3.5(0.10)
Both Arb./Str.	27(24.3)	3.7(0.08)
One of Arb./Str.	39(35.1)	3.5(0.08)
Other	28(25.2)	3.6(0.08)

Table 1: Summary statistics of factor variables

2.3 Statistical Methods

We analyzed these data using a multiple linear regression model with GPA as the single response variable, y . The explanatory variables were all treated as factor variables with levels described in Table ?. The factor variables are denoted by $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_p)^T$. The statistical linear model assumed on the population is given below,

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \dots + \beta_p x_p + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where the β s are the regression effects, p is the total number of factor levels of \mathbf{x} , and ϵ represents the error term.

Linear regression is one of the most widely utilized statistical model due to its practical interpretation of model parameters and closed form solution for parameter estimation [5]. For example, β_1 can be interpreted as the expected change in y for every unit increase in x_1 when all other explanatory variables remain constant. Since our data consists of factor variables, the interpretation is altered slightly to properly interpret effects relative to the baseline group. Namely, as the expected change in y for group x_1 compared to the baseline group when all other explanatory variable remain constant. See Section 3 for specific interpretations for our modeling results.

We fit model (1) to our data utilizing the statistical language R (version 4.2.1) via the interface RStudio (version 2023.09.1+494). In particular, we employed model (1) by applying the $\text{lm}(y \sim \mathbf{x})$ function in the *stats* R package. In linear regression, parameter estimates are found by minimizing the sum of the square errors (or residuals): $\sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon_i^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$

where n is the sample size and $\hat{y}_i = b_0 + b_1 x_{1i} + \dots + b_p x_{pi}$ with (b_0, b_1, \dots, b_p) representing the estimates for parameters $(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)$, respectively [2]. Multiple linear regression has five model assumptions that need to be met in order for parameter estimates, interpretations, and statistical significance to be valid [2]:

A1. Explanatory variables are linearly associated with the response variable.

A2. Residuals are normally distributed.

A3. Variance of the residuals is constant across the dependent variable space.

A4. Residuals are independent of one another.

A5. Explanatory variables are not highly correlated with one another

We also apply step-wise variable selection on our multiple regression model using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) in order to increase the statistical power of our model and to assess which variables are the most statistically associated with GPA. There are several measures available to assess model fit in variable selection, such as, e.g., the Akaike Information criterion (AIC), and the maximum log-likelihood. We opt to utilize BIC as this criterion is optimal when the modelling objective is oriented around feature selection as opposed to prediction [5].

3 Results/Conclusion

We applied model (1) to our data on 112 students using GPA as the response variable and the factor variables listed in Table 1 as the explanatory variables. In this section, we provide the modeling results and offer valuable insights into the factors potentially influencing GPA. Table 2 provides results of the 2-population difference in means t-test for the GPA between students who engage in both aerobic and strength training for a moderate duration (240-480min/wk) and students who do not exercise at all. The no exercise group had a 3.48 mean GPA, while the moderate/both exercise group had a higher GPA of 3.84. The p-value, 0.01, of this t-test indicates high statistical significance, in particular, we conclude that the students in the moderate/both exercise group have a significantly higher GPA than those who do exercise at all. We can interpret this practically by providing the relative change between the mean GPAs, i.e., students who engage in both aerobic and strength training for a moderate duration have a 10.4% higher GPA than those who don't exercise at all.

Mod/Both Exercise (N = 10)	No Exercise (N = 17)			
Mean GPA (SE)	Mean GPA (SE)	95% CI	T	p-value
3.84 (0.08)	3.48 (0.11)	(0.08, 0.64)	2.65	0.013*

Table 2: Results of difference of means t-test for GPA in moderate weekly amount of aerobic and strength population vs. no exercise population

Table 3 provides the statistical results in the form of the coefficient estimate, standard, p-value for each factor variable level of our multiple regression model. The variables, age and class standing were significantly associated with GPA. In particular, the age group of students 26-35 years old have a 0.59 point lower GPA on average ($p=0.01$) compared to students 18 - 20 years old and all other variables held constant. In terms of class standing, seniors have a 0.41 point lower GPA on average ($p=0.003$) compared to freshmen when all other variables are held constant. Table 3 also suggests those in the mod/both exercise group have a 0.24 point higher GPA on average compared to those who do not exercises at all. The corresponding p-value ($p=0.015$) is not statistically significant; however, it does provide some moderate evidence of a difference in GPA. The baseline group of the model consists of art majors, students 18-20 years old, male, freshmen, stress level of 2, have dependents, studies 0 -5 hours per week, and do not exercise.

Variable	Estimate	SE	p-value
Age (years)			
21 -25	0.09	0.14	0.507
26 -35	-0.59	0.22	0.010**
Gender			
Female	-0.07	0.10	0.480
Other	0.53	0.35	0.134
Class Standing			
Sophomore	-0.20	0.14	0.152
Junior	-0.32	0.17	0.051
Senior	-0.41	0.14	0.003**
Stress Level (0-5)			
3	-0.05	0.22	0.82
4	-0.20	0.19	0.312
5	-0.06	0.20	0.77
6	-0.17	0.22	0.44
Dependent(s)			
No	0.21	0.25	0.391
Studying (hrs/wk)			
5 -10	-0.17	0.13	0.185
10 -15	0.09	0.14	0.510
15 -20	0.02	0.18	0.891
> 20	0.17	0.19	0.381
Major College			
BUS/ECON	-0.32	0.27	0.251
COMM	-0.27	0.31	0.387
EDU	-0.09	0.45	0.836
ENG/CPSC	-0.36	0.25	0.160
HE/HUDV	-0.38	0.28	0.182
HUM/SOSC	-0.16	0.25	0.521
NSM	-0.29	0.25	0.250
Exercise (Dur./Type)			
Min/Both	0.20	0.41	0.632
Min/One	0.14	0.15	0.354
Min/Other	0.26	0.21	0.219
Low/Both	0.11	0.16	0.509
Low/One	-0.19	0.16	0.227
Low/Other	-0.07	0.18	0.710
Mod/Both	0.24	0.16	0.155
Mod/One	-0.18	0.20	0.359
Mod/Other	0.10	0.20	0.627
High/Both	0.04	0.21	0.823
High/One	-0.07	0.17	0.691
High/Other	-0.28	0.17	0.113

Table 3: Multiple regression model results. Baseline group: ART majors, students 18-20 years old, male, freshmen, stress level of 2, have dependents, studies 0-5 hours/wk, and do not exercise.

The assumptions (A1-A4) for the linear regression model can be assessed by looking at the plots provided Figure 4. The Residuals vs Fitted plot does not show any patterns in

the residuals across the fitted values, which suggests that the explanatory variables do have a linear association with the response variable. The range of the residuals across the fitted values are roughly constant with a few outliers. However, the Residuals vs Leverage plot shows that the outliers are not influential. The Normal Q-Q plot shows that the residuals are heavy on both the negative and positive tails. This is mostly due to the non-influential outliers. To assess normality further, we performed a Shapiro-Wilks normality test on the residuals. In this test, the null hypothesis is that the data are normally distributed. The resulting p-value for our test was $p = 0.07108$, so we failed to reject the null. Therefore, we can conclude that the normality assumption is not violated. In regards to collinearity (A5), we can refer to the correlation matrix in Figure 1, and note that most of the correlations amongst the explanatory variables are very weak. The only notable correlation, r , is between class standing and age, at $r = 0.68$.

Figure 4: Graphical assessments for the assumptions of the full linear regression model.

We performed a step-wise variable selection method using BIC, in order to increase the statistical power of our model and to assess which variables are the most statistically associated with GPA. Table 4 provides the results of the step-wise variable selection procedure that was performed. Note that exercise was forced to stay in the model since that is our variable of interest. Students in age group of 26-35 have an effect estimate of -0.59 and seniors have an effect estimate of -0.4 (Table 3), which changed to steeper negative effect estimates of -0.65 and -0.45 (Table 4). The moderate/both exercise group showed an equivalent effect estimate of 0.24 in the step-wise variable BIC selection (Table 3 and 4). However, the BIC step-wise variable selected model has a smaller p-value of $p = 0.11$, (Table 4) compared to $p = 0.15$ (Table 3). Overall, the full model and the reduced model results

in similar effect estimates for notable variable factor levels, with the reduced model having associated smaller p-values. However, we cannot fully rely on the reduced model since the normality assumption becomes violated; Shapiro-Wilks, $p = 0.0007$ and Figure 5. However, all other model assumptions appear to be reasonably met (refer to Figure 5).

Variable	Estimate	SE	p-value
Age (years)			
21 -25	0.13	12	0.292
26 -35	-0.65	0.21	0.003**
Class Standing			
Sophomore	-0.19	0.12	0.134
Junior	-0.25	0.14	0.071
Senior	-0.45	0.12	0.0002**
Exercise (Dur./Type)			
Min/Both	0.26	0.37	0.496
Min/One	0.09	0.14	0.508
Min/Other	0.31	0.19	0.101
Low/Both	0.09	0.15	0.546
Low/One	-0.17	0.14	0.253
Low/Other	-0.03	0.15	0.838
Mod/Both	0.24	0.15	0.111
Mod/One	-0.15	0.18	0.407
Mod/Other	0.04	0.18	0.842
High/Both	0.03	0.18	0.854
High/One	0.01	0.15	0.900
High/Other	-0.15	0.16	0.341

Table 4: Multiple regression model results after step-wise AIC variable selection. Baseline group: ART majors, students 18-20 years old, male, freshmen, stress level of 2, have dependents, studies 0-5 hours/wk, and do not exercise.

Figure 5: Graphical assessments for the assumptions of the reduced linear regression model.

4 Discussion

A foremost discussion point is to note the potential challenges in working with voluntary response survey data. In any observational study, statistically causal conclusions cannot be made due to potential confounding variables, response bias, and non-response bias [2]. For example, one potential confounding factor may be household income. Students with higher incomes have a higher likelihood of having tutors, non-campus gym memberships, and/or being involved in private sport groups. In terms of non-response bias, we suspect that we have a sizeable non-response bias amongst students who have lower GPAs as students with lower GPAs may be less inclined to share that information freely. Finally, response bias may

be present in the reporting of exercise duration in that answering the question relied on the respondents recall of their activities rather than exact measurement of time spent exercising - duration may have easily been under or over estimated. A final important note to make is that the GPA of freshman respondents may have been their highschool GPA as freshman have not yet received college letter grades during their first college semester. However, class standing was a variable that we controlled for in our model.

In regards to the relationship between exercise and GPA, we conclude that further data need be collected in order to explore this correlation fully. When considering the association between exercise duration and type marginally with GPA, we found no correlation, which is counter intuitive to the current literature. However, when we considered the interaction between exercise duration and type, our results suggests there could be an increase in GPA for students who engage in a combination of aerobic and strength training for a moderate weekly duration (Tables 2, 3, and 4). Our findings have directed our future research focus on further investigating specifically the interaction effect of exercise type and duration on GPA in a more controlled setting.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my mentor, Dr. Poynor, for her exceptional mentorship and insightful feedback; her expertise and knowledge were invaluable during this research. Additionally, I extend sincere gratitude to the CSUF honors program and its faculty for their support and guidance, which significantly contributed to the development and enrichment of the research presented in this paper.

References

- [1] R. Bruffaerts, P. Mortier, G. Kiekens, R.P. Auerbach, P. Cuipers, K. Demyttenaera, J.G. Green, M.K. Nock, and R.C. Kessler. Mental health problems in college freshmen: Prevalence and academic functioning. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 225:97–103, 2018.
- [2] D Diez, M.Ç etinkaya Rundel, and C.D. Barr. *OpenIntro Statistics*. OpenIntro, 2019.
- [3] K.I. Erickson, C. Hillman, C. Stillman, M. Chelsea, R.M. Ballard, B. Bloodgood, D.E. Conroy, R. Macko, D.X. Marquez, J. Steven, and E. Kenneth. Physical activity, cognition and brain outcomes: A review of the 2018 physical activity guidelines. *Med. Sci. Sports Exerc.*, 51(6):1242–1251, 2018.
- [4] K. Hötting and B. Röder. Beneficial effects of physical exercise on neuroplasticity and cognition. *Neuroscience and biobehavioral reviews*, 37(9 Pt B):2243–2257, 2013.
- [5] G. James, W. Daniela, T. Hastie, and R. Tibshirani. *An Introduction to Statistical Learning with applications in R*. Springer, 2013.
- [6] C. Kim, Y. Song, and Y.J. Jeon. The effect of college students' physical activity level on depression and personal relationships. *Healthcare*, 9(5):526, 2021.
- [7] C. Di Liegro, G. Schiera, and I. De Liegro. Physical activity and brain health. <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-4425/10/9/720>, 2019. Accessed: April 19, 2023.
- [8] T.W. Lin and Y.M. Kuo. Exercise benefits brain function: The monamine connection. *Brain Science*, 3(4):39–53, 2013.
- [9] C.M. Wright, P.J. Duquesnay, S. Anzman-Frasca, V.R. Chomitz, K. Chui, C.D. Economos, E.G. Langevin, M.E. Nelson, and J.M. Satchek. Study protocol: The fueling learning through exercise (flex) study: a randomized controlled trial of the impact of school-based physical activity programs on children's physical activity, cognitive function, and academic achievement. *BMC Public Health*, 16(1), 2016.